

Kivelson and Neiman¹⁰ have shown that g_{II} is a moderately sensitive function for indicating covalency. Normally g_{II} is 2.3 or more for ionic environment and it is less than 2.3 for covalent environments. The present result shows that g_{II} is less than 2.3, suggesting that the complex is covalent in nature. Similar observations were also made with other ($S = \frac{1}{2}$) copper complexes¹¹.

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Hydrogen Ion Equilibria on *p*-Toluenesulphonylated Casein

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THE role of surface active agents in affecting changes in the biological systems is well recognised. They exert disruptive influence on the cell membrane¹, act as tuberculostatic agents², increase the concentration of sulphones on the cell surface, form complexes with proteins^{3,4} (albumin-sodium alkyl sulphate complexes). Sulphonylated proteins are also known for their physiological activity.

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In view of the above it was envisaged that modified proteins can serve as good models to understand the nature of such reactions. As a first step, investigation to determine their reaction sites is necessary. It was best achieved by carrying out hydrogen ion equilibria studies by various workers particularly Linderstrom⁵, Tanford⁶, Cannon⁷, Malik⁸⁻¹⁰.

This paper gives the result of hydrogen equilibria studies on *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein along with those on the binding of H⁺ and OH⁻ ions to whole casein reported earlier¹¹.

Experimental

Solution : *p*-Toluene sulphonylated casein used was prepared by the method of Gurin and Clarke¹². Sulphur content was found to be 1.945%. Solution of *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein was prepared at pH 6.5, using KOH. Its concentration was determined by drying a known aliquot at 105°. The correction for potassium ions was applied to get the absolute weight of protein. Carbonate free hydroxide was prepared as recommended by Kolthoff¹³. Potassium chloride, potassium hydrogen phthalate and sodium borate solutions were prepared by dissolving A. R. samples in doubly distilled water.

Apparatus and techniques : pH measurements were made on Beckmann model G pH meter, using glass electrodes. The pH meter was standardised by measuring the pH of 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate for the acid range and that of 0.01 M sodium borate for the alkali range. Purified nitrogen was passed slowly for about 10 min to ensure inert atmosphere.

Optical density was measured with Unicam spectrophotometer type SP 500, using a hydrogen lamp (slit width 0.1 mm and silica cells of 1 cm path).

Procedure : Varying amount of hydrochloric acid (0.0861 M), viz. 2.0, 1.6, 1.0, 0.8, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1 and 0.02 ml and 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.1, 1.2 and 1.5 ml of potassium hydroxide (0.0605 M) were taken in different pyrex tubes. Two such sets were prepared. In one set, protein was not added and total volume was made upto 10.0 ml by adding 1.5 ml of 1.0 M potassium chloride (to maintain constant ionic strength) and water. In the second set, the total volume was made 10 ml, by adding 4 ml of *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein solution (2.0%) and 1.5 ml of 1.0 M potassium chloride solution and water. The pH values of these solutions were then recorded at two different temperatures, viz., 20° and 30°. The results are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Experiments were also performed to show the reversible nature of hydrogen ion equilibria of the protein both in the acidic and basic range¹⁴ of pH. The hydrogen ion titration curve was found to be reversible at moderate pH values.

TABLE 1—HYDROGEN ION BINDING DATA ON p-T. S. CASEIN AT 20°

H ⁺ added (moles/ litre × 10 ⁻³)	Ionic strength Total volume Protein concentration		Bound H ⁺ mole/10 ⁵ g of protein	Moles H ⁺ dissociated per 10 ⁵ g of protein
	pH ₁ (without protein)	pH ₂ (with protein)		
17.22	1.9	2.2	108	38
13.78	2.1	2.4	108	38
8.61	2.25	2.5	92	49
6.89	2.35	4.0	84	57
4.31	2.45	4.9	54	87
2.58	2.55	5.3	32	109
0.86	3.1	5.7	11	130
0.17	3.70	6.0	2	139

OH⁻ added
(moles/
litre 10⁻³)

1.21	10.1	7.0	15	156
2.42	10.2	7.55	30	171
3.63	10.3	8.8	44	185
4.84	11.0	9.05	59	200
6.05	11.25	9.55	75	216
6.65	11.35	10.35	75	216
7.26	11.5	10.75	75	216
9.08	11.9	11.0	99	240

Fig. 1, Curve (a)

TABLE 2°—HYDROGEN ION BINDING DATA ON p-T. S. CASEIN AT 30°

H ⁺ added (moles/ litre × 10 ⁻³)	Ionic strength Total volume Protein concentration		Bound H ⁺ mole/10 ⁵ g of protein	Moles H ⁺ dissociated per 10 ⁵ g of protein
	pH ₁ (without protein)	pH ₂ (with protein)		
0.17	3.60	5.85	2	139
1.21	9.40	6.90	15	156
2.42	10.10	7.40	30	171
3.63	10.25	8.60	44	185
4.84	10.90	8.80	60	201
6.05	11.00	9.25	75	216
6.65	11.05	10.05	75	216
7.26	11.20	10.45	75	216
9.08	11.55	10.75	98	239

* Data below pH 6.0 are the same as at 20° hence not included.

Fig. 1, Curve (b)

To determine the ratio of tyrosine and tryptophan groups of the protein, it was dissolved in 0.1 N KOH and optical densities were measured at 281 and 294 nm. The results are given in Table 3.

Calculations The bound hydrogen and hydroxyl ions were determined by the following relationships^{6,7}

TABLE 3—PROTEIN CONCENTRATION=8.0 g/litre
IONIC STRENGTH=0.15
TEMPERATURE=20° AND 30°

pH, at 20°	pH, at 30°	Moles of H ⁺ dissociated per 10 ⁵ g of protein	ΔH _{ion} × 10 ³
4.0	3.95	57	1.9365
4.90	4.85	87	1.9365
5.80	5.25	109	1.9865
5.70	5.65	130	1.9865
6.00	5.95	139	1.9365
7.00	6.90	156	3.8700
7.55	7.40	171	5.8000
8.80	8.60	185	7.7460
9.05	8.80	200	9.6800
10.95	10.05	216	11.6100
10.75	10.45	216	11.6100
11.05	10.70	240	13.5500

Fig. 2

$(C_1 - C_2)/g = C_1/g [1 - \text{antilog}(pH_1 - pH_2)]$
for bound hydrogen ions and
 $(C_1 - C_2)/g = C_1/g [1 - \text{antilog}(pH_2 - pH_1)]$
for bound hydroxyl ions, where g is weight of the protein in gm, C₁ and C₂ are the concentration in gm moles/litre of the acid with and without the protein and pH₁ and pH₂ are the corresponding pH values. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The apparent heat of ionisation (ΔH_{ion}) was determined according to Wyman's^{1,2} method using the equation

$$\Delta H_{ion} = -2.303RT^2 \left(\frac{dpH}{dt} \right)_{\gamma}$$

where dpH is the change in pH with change in temperature dt at a fixed value of γ (the number of hydrogen ion dissociated per 10⁵ g of protein).

The ratio of tyrosine and tryptophan groups was calculated by the method of Beaven and Holiday^{1,2} using the following formula:

$$\frac{M_{Tyrosine}}{M_{Tryptophan}} = \frac{0.592 E_{280} - 0.263 E_{294}}{0.263 E_{280} - 0.170 E_{294}}$$

where E₂₈₀ and E₂₉₄ are the extinction coefficients of the protein in 0.1 N KOH at 280 nm and 294 nm.

As the exact molecular weight of p-toluene sulphonylated casein is not known, all the calculations have been made for 10⁵ g of the protein.

Results and Discussion

The results on hydrogen ion equilibria studies of p-toluene sulphonylated casein, worked out at two different temperatures, viz. 20° and 30°, provide valuable information regarding the different ionisable groups present in the protein. The whole titration curve may be divided into three different portions by the method of Cannon^{1,2}, each region corresponding to a set of intrinsically identical groups:

(i) The first region is attributed to the ionisation of those side chain carboxyl groups not present as amides (α-carboxyl at the end of peptide chain

Fig. 1. Titration curves of *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein.

and β -carboxyl group from aspartyl and glutamyl residues of the protein).

(ii) The second region is attributed to the imidazole groups from the histidine residue.

(iii) The third region is not always defined and is due to α -amino (at the end of the peptide chain), ϵ -amino groups of lysine, phenolic hydroxyl groups of tyrosine residues, guanidinium groups of arginine residues.

The titration curves at high and low pH values permit an estimation of the maximum base and acid combining capacity of *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein. In addition to the usual ionising groups found in most proteins, the *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein contains amount of phosphoric acid just like whole casein that must be considered in an analysis for the anionic groups. According to Cannon *et al*¹⁷ a phosphate group in egg albumin may be expected to contribute two equivalents to the titration curve, one in the carboxyl region at about pH 2 and the other in the imidazole region at about pH 7.0. It is not easy to establish from these curves definite transition points representing the ionisation of specific groups. pH values of 6.35 and 9.30 have been selected since these values give the results from α -, β - and γ -casein¹⁸ and agree with the analytical data of Gordan *et al*¹¹. They are also consistent with the values given by Scatchard¹⁹ for the binding of hydrogen ions for the various types of groups in other proteins under similar condition. At pH 6.35, the titration curves give the number of carboxyl groups plus one equivalent of phosphoric acid and at pH 9.3 give the number of carboxyl groups plus imidazole groups and two equivalent of

phosphoric acid. Based on the pH values, the calculated values for the ionising groups for α -, β - and γ -casein are in agreement with analytical results for α -, β - and γ -casein¹⁸.

The carboxyl region: The upper portion of titration curve of *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein obtained at 20° [Fig. 1, curve (a)] represents the dissociation of hydrogen ion from phosphoric acid and the carboxyl group of *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein and hence may be used to determine the number of these groups. It is clear from Fig. 1, curve (a) that at pH about 6.35, the curve starts flattening, indicating complete ionisation of the carboxyl and phosphate groups. The value of γ at pH 6.35 comes out to be 140. This value finds further support from the data of apparent heat of ionisation (Fig. 2) since sharp inflexion occurs at $\gamma=140$ corresponding to $\Delta H_{ion}=1.936$ Kcals/10⁵ g of protein. This value is within the expected range of carboxyl groups (Table 4).

The non-carboxyl region: The expected range of ionisation of imidazole groups of protein is between pH 6.35 to pH 9.3 and hence the value of the number of hydrogen ions dissociated per 10⁵ g of protein between this range may be utilised to determine the number of imidazole groups. This value comes out to be 18 at pH 9.3. The results on apparent heat of ionisation for these groups also support the above data since ΔH value of 6.8 Kcals/10⁵ g of protein, which is the expected value for these groups, is obtained (Table 4).

The analysis of the basic portion of the curve (i.e. beyond pH 9.3) is difficult to explain due to overlapping of the titration regions of different

Fig. 2. Relation between apparent heat of ionization and the total no. of H⁺ dissociated per 10⁵ grms of protein.

TABLE 4—APPARENT HEAT OF IONISATION OF IONISING GROUPS OF *p*-TOLUENE SULPHONYLATED CASEIN

Ionisable groups	Expected range for ΔH _{ion} (Kcal)	Observed average value for ΔH _{ion} (Kcal)
Carboxyl	±1.5-3.0	1.9365
Imidazole	7.0	6.800
Amino	10-12	—
Guanidinium	12-14	13.600

groups. However, the average value of γ between 9.3 and 10.5 (expected range for the ionisation of amino groups in proteins) may be taken as the number of total amino groups present in *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein. However, it has been found from the titration curve (Fig. 1) that no change in the number of hydrogen ions dissociated per 10⁵ g of protein is observed beyond pH 9.3. The constancy upto pH 10.5 shown by the flat portion in the hydrogen ion titration curves [Fig. 1, curves (a), (b)] is due to the masking of the amino group of the protein as a result of sulphonylation. This fact has been further supported by the result of apparent heat of ionisation (Fig. 2).

Arginine is not directly estimated by titration since guanidino groups are too strong a base to be converted to the unified form in any significant amount at any pH (even upto 11) where accurate measurement is possible. Beyond this pH, the titration data do not give reliable results. The results

on apparent heat of ionisation comes out to be 22, corresponding the ΔH_{ion} value of 13.55 Kcals/10⁵ g of protein (Fig. 2).

Tyrosine and tryptophan groups: Since potentiometric method could not be used as such to determine the number of these groups, spectrophotometric method was employed to determine the ratio of these groups. The spectrophotometric value of 5.14 for the ratio of these groups is in close resemblance with analytical²⁰ value of 5.83 for these groups.

A comparison of the hydrogen ion equilibria data of *p*-toluene sulphonylated casein with that of casein is given in Table 5.

TABLE 5—IONISABLE GROUPS IN NATIVE CASEIN AND *p*-TOLUENE SULPHONYLATED CASEIN

Groups	Reasonable* analytical values in Casein/10 ⁵ g	Observed in case of <i>p</i> -T.S. Casein/10 ⁵ g	Observed in case of <i>p</i> -T.S. Gelatin/10 ⁵ g
α-Carboxyl	96	94.0	110
β-Carboxyl			4
Imidazole	20	18.00	—
Amino	56	—	42
Guanidinium	23.5	22	—
Tyrosine/Tryp.	5.83	5.14	46
Total Cationic	100	40	—

* Reference 11.

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